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Study on the Health Status of Tribal Women in India

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Abstract :- Health is a most important for human beings and also fundamental human right. It means every individual has right to access all sorts of medical services, enough quality food, good housing for their well being. According to World Health Organization it is a "State of complete physical, mental, and social well being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity". The Scheduled Tribes are one of the most disadvantaged sections of the Indian population. They are deprived of basic amenities like education health, education, sanitation and pure drinking water and excluded from the development process. Government of India has undertaken several programs policies have been under taken ever since independence towards improvements of health and education. Despite the various comprehensive policies and measures, the health status of Tribal women is poor compared to rest of the population. The present paper discusses the health status of Tribal Women in India. The objectives of this study are to study the health status of Tribal Women, to identify the Health Problem of Tribal Women and to assess the Government health Schemes for women in India. The intended study based on secondary sources of data like books, journals, articles, census reports and Economic Survey and e-sources. The study reveals that majority of the tribal women facing the problem of maternal health, and pursues unhygienic practices, Nutritional anaemia. The study concludes Government should provides, better health centre, nutritional food and create awareness about health programme for the betterment of women health in the future India.

Keywords :- Health Status, initiatives, Nutritional status, Tribal Women.

Introduction :- Health is important for human beings, it is fundamental for human rights. It

means every individual has the right to the maximum possible access standard of physical and mental health such as medical services, sanitation, sufficient food, affordable housing. World Health Organization, defines it is a "State of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not only the absence of illness or frailty"¹ (Shashi Rani Dev2016). It has played a pivotal role in the development of a country by the way of the wellbeing of human beings. Human development is mainly associated with improvements in the health status of human beings. The comprised Index of Human Development Index (HDI) introduced by UNDP includes three components as health, education, and income-generating capacity² (Salil Basu 2000). Health plays a pivotal role in the process of society-cultural, economic, educational, social, and political development³ (Srivastva. P 2015). Improvements in the health status of the population in the country have been the focal point component of the development policy under the various planning periods⁴ (Annual Report 2006-07). The Scheduled Tribes are the most susceptible sections of Indian society.

As per the 2011 census, about 8.6 percent of STs are registered in the country⁵ (Census 2011). Improved access to the essential services in health and education, especially for the poor, is essential to ensure inclusiveness and also to support rapid growth⁶ (Satyanarayana, G., Raju and Madhusudana, H.S. 2013). STs are deprived of basic amenities like health, education, sanitation, and pure drinking water. The Government of India has been initiated a major health component for STs ever independence, with massive disbursement of funds for human resource and infrastructure development. Further comprehensive measures have been undertaken for the development of sanitation, pure drinking water, communication,

and education. Notwithstanding the initiatives and interventions of the Governments, the health status of STs is not improved at a faster rate as compared to the rest of the population and is far below the national average⁷(Snehalata Panda 2015). In the above backdrop, the intended study focused on the Health Status of Tribal Women in India –An Overview is taken for the study.

Status of Tribal Women :- The sex ratio is one of the indicators to use to recognize the status of males and females in the country. The Sex ratio of STs registered 990, is higher than the national average of 943. The Sex ratio of STs increased to 990 from 978 has improved during the census period 2001 to 2011. The states Goa, Kerala, Arunachal Pradesh, Odisha, Chhattisgarh, etc., have shown the highest followed by Jammu & Kashmir has exposed the lowest sex ratio of STs at 924 in the 2011 census¹³(Annual Report 2019-20).

Access to better education, health, employment, and ability to decisions making are the factors to improve the status of a person or group in society. These factors are determining the status of an individual or a society. Improve the educational status will lead to improve the health status, grab employment opportunities and increase in decision-making ability of these groups. The health status of the tribal is poor as compared to the national average. The health indicators infant mortality rate, the fertility rate is high among tribals in the country. They are not aware of diseases and health care, provision of drinking water, and hygiene¹⁴ (Pujasree Chatterjee 2014). In a tribal society, women are playing a predominant role in the improvement of social status and Social justice. Improvement of social status can be accessed on the basis of the level of income, work participation rate, access to employment opportunities, access to quality health, intake of nutrition food, and the important role within their family, community, and society¹⁵ (Ghosh, 1987). The importance of tribal women in tribal communities is more considerable and crucial. Women play a crucial role in tribal society than in the other social

groups, due to their work hard, and maintain family, after industrialization the importance of tribal women is significant by gathering minor forest produce¹⁶ (Yamanoorappa Yenkoba Talavar and Manikamma Nagindrappa 2014).The literacy rate of tribal women increased to 49.35 per cent from 34.76 per cent during the census 2001-2011. It was about 64.64 per cent from 53.67 per cent of the general population¹⁷ (Census 2011.)

Health Status of Tribal Women in India :-

Improved health status of individuals not only indicates greater human development but also is an important parameter of economic development. About 65 per cent of tribal women in between age group 15-49 are found anaemic¹⁸ (India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare). According to National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) (2014) data reveals that about 27 percent of the delivery cases in tribal women still at home¹⁹ (National Sample Survey Office). Further the infant mortality rate in ST population registered about 74 as against 62 of the all social groups²⁰(National family health survey (NFHS-4) 2012-14). In the same way, maternal mortality rate (MMR) is about 57 (National Family Health Survey-4). The details of health indicators and status of the tribal women, as well as all categories are presented in table 1.

Table 1
Health Status of Tribal Women and General Population in India

Indicators	Scheduled Tribes		General Population	
	2005-06	2015-16	2005-06	2015-16
Infant Mortality Rate(IMR)	62.1	44.4	57	40.7
Under Five Mortality Rate(USMR)	95.7	57.2	74.3	49.7
Percentage of Women Under of age 15-49 with any anemia(haemoglobin level< than 12.0 grams per deciliter)	68.5	59.8	55.3	53
Percentage of Children of age 06-59 month with any anaemia(haemoglobin level< than 11.0grams per deciliter)	76.8	63.1	69.5	58.4

Source: Annual Report 2020-21 Government of India, Ministry of Tribal Affair, pp.37-38

It is evident from the table 1 that the health indicators depicts that , Infant Mortality Rate, Under Five Mortality Rate and Anemia in women and children for All category and Scheduled Tribes, have considerably improved from 2005-06 (NFHS 3) to 2015-16(NFHS-4) but as compared to general population there is gap between STs and General population.

Malnutrition Status :- The malnutrition status of the tribal women is very high; it is proved from several studies. The children under below 5 years are also very high. According to National Family Health Survey Report-4, reveals that even though gradual improvements in health indicators, the undernutrition among STs has remained poor, and much higher than that of all social groups in the country. It is evident from the report that about 44 per cent of the tribal children under five years of age are stunted (low height for age), 45 per cent are underweight (low weight for age) and 27 per cent are wasted (low weight for height). The inefficiency of nutritional status leads to diseases like endemic goiter, anemia, pellagra, and beriberi. Problems like in-sanitary food supplies, water contamination, and poor food intake reflect on the health status of tribals²¹ (Dandub Palzor Negi and Monica Munjial Singh 2020).Majority of the tribal women facing the problem of maternal health and pursue unhygienic practices, Nutritional anaemia. According to the census report, 2011 reveals that 11 per cent of the tribal households have access to tap water and only 3 per cent of the tap water from the treated source. The poor connectivity of water results in a deficiency in health and related diseases. The most common diseases found among tribals are respiratory tract infections and diarrheal disorders. About 21 per cent of children suffer at least two bouts of diarrhea every year and 22 per cent suffer from at least two attacks of respiratory infections²² (Census 2011).

Nutritional Status :- The nutritional status among women as measured by the BMI is directly related to the dietary intake²³ (Vijay Kumar Baraik and P M Kulkarni2006). Food is a pre-requisite not only for attaining good health but also for maintaining adequate growth and body equilibrium. The choice of quality food depends on level of income, higher the income leads to access quality of foods and improvements in health.

Nutritional Status of Children under 5 years :- Based on data of National Family Health Survey (NFHS)-3& 4 during 2005-06 and 2015-16 Nutritional Status of Children under 5 years is shown in below table 2.

Table 2
Nutritional Status of Children under 5 years

Parameter	Scheduled Tribes		General Population	
	2005-06	2015-16	2005-06	2015-16
Stunted	53.9	43.8	48	38.4
Wasted	27.6	27.4	19.8	21
Under Wight	54.5	45.3	42.5	35.7

Source: Annual Report 2020-21 Government of India, Ministry of Tribal Affair, p-38

It has been observed from the above table that the nutritional status of children under 5 years shows improvement during the period from 2005-06 to 2015-16. It is found that Stunted (height-for-age), declined to 43.8 from 53.9. In the case of the general population, it was 38.4 from 48 and in Wasted (weight-for-height) about 27.4 from 27.6. In respect of the general population, it was increased 21 from 19.8 in the above said period. As per underweight is concerned it was decreased to 45.3 from 54.5 and 35.7 from 42.7 respectively. It is observed from the interpretation that there is a significant improvement in the health status of STs Children and the general population. It may the reason effective implementation of health schemes for women and children in the country.

Vaccination Coverage of Children :- Status of ST and All category children aged 12-23 months who received full immunization and no vaccination are given in Table 3

Table 3
ST and All category children Full Immunization / No Vaccination

Source	Full Immunization (%)		No Vaccination (%)	
	ST	All	ST	All
NFHS-3 (2005-06)	31.3	43.5	11.5	5.1
NFHS-4 (2015-16)	55.8	62.0	9.2	6.0

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS), M/o H&FW

It can be seen from table 3 that details of children aged 12-23 months who received Full Immunization / No Vaccination among STs and all category children. It is found that full immunization increased to 55.8 per cent from 31.3 per cent for STs. In the case of all categories 62.0 per cent from 43.5 per cent and as regard no vaccination is concerned it was declined to 9.2 per cent from 11.5 per cent among STs and in the case of General population, it was increased to 6.0 per cent from 5.1 per cent respectively. It is clear from the analysis there are improvements in immunization both STs and the general population but when no vaccination is concern the STs are decreased as compared to the rest of the population. It may be ignorance of the STs about vaccination.

Institutional Delivery :- Institutional delivery is also one of the significant factors that play an important role in the improvement of the health status of tribal women. It is found that there is a significant improvement from 17.7 per cent to 68 per cent during the period from 2005-06 to 2015-16. In the case of all categories, it was about from 38.7 per cent to 78.9 per cent in the same period. The tribal women attended deliveries attended by skilled health personnel have augmented drastically from 25.4 per cent to 71.5 per cent in the above said period, but there is a gap between tribal women and all social groups women in India²⁴(Annual Report 2020-21).

Maternal Mortality & Maternal Health :- According to National Family Health Survey-3, reveals that scheduled tribe mother having

received the lowest likelihood of care from a doctor, it was about 32.8 per cent as compared to 50.2 per cent all India. In the case of antenatal care for their birth, is received advice about where to go if they experienced pregnancy complications which are about 32.4 percent of ST mothers is the lowest of all social groups in the country. Further, about 17.7 per cent of births to ST mothers are delivered in health facilities as compared to 51 per cent of births to mothers in all social groups. The reduction of maternal and neonatal mortality is only possible by trained obstetric care providers during the delivery period. It is evident that out of the 47.4 per cent of birth to women in the country merely 17.1 per cent of births to ST women was assisted by a doctor²⁵ (Statistical Profile of Scheduled Tribes in India 2013).

Health Problem of Tribal Women in India :-

Health and nutrition and are the problems of tribal women which are varied from the various groups. In rural areas, nutritional anaemia is a major problem for women in India as well as in the tribal community. It is a most serious fact because of their heavy workload and anaemia has a deep effect on psychological and physical health²⁶ (Salil Basu (2000)). The maternal health, and pursues unhygienic practices, due to their ignorance about the health-related schemes and programmes of the government. The higher infant mortality rate is high among Tribals due to malnutrition. The nutritional status and life expectancy are very lower among tribals than the national average and also higher fertility rate in tribal women. Due to their ignorance about the use of scientific information concerning health and diseases and belief in gullible cures for diseases their socio-cultural and economic rights, and involvement in management, access to employment, food, health, etc. In the Tribal community, most of the tribal women work hard on par with males at lower wages, sexual exploitation. Despite the special programme to control widespread diseases malaria, continued to affect people. The diseases like diarrhoea, tuberculosis, chickenpox, meningitis, and another vector, air, and water-borne diseases have not

abated. Morbidity and mortality rates are high due to malnutrition and anemia²⁷ (Pujasree Chatterjee 2014).

Findings :-

- The study proved that gender based violence; domestic violence is high among tribal women in India. About 65 per cent of tribal women in between age group 15-49 are found anaemic and 27 percent of the delivery cases in tribal women still at home
- It is evident that the health status like mortality, morbidity and malnutrition rates have significantly improved from 2005-06 (NFHS 3) to 2015-16(NFHS-4) but as compared to general population there is gap between STs and General population.
- The study reveals that majority of the tribal women facing the problem of maternal health, and pursues unhygienic practices, Nutritional anaemia.
- The study found that violence. Sexual physical attack, inequity and embarrassment have increased in the country.
- It is clear from the analysis there are improvements in immunization both STs and the general population but when no vaccination is concern the STs are decreased as compared to the rest of the population.
- The nutritional status and life expectancy are very lower among tribals women than the national average and also higher fertility rate in tribal women.
- The study found that diseases like diarrhoea, tuberculosis, chickenpox, meningitis, and another vector, air, and water-borne diseases have not abated. Morbidity and mortality rates are high due to malnutrition and anemia

Suggestlons :-

- Government should implement effective educational, housing and health schemes for the improvement of health status of tribal women in India.
- Immediate action should be taken for the

health care facilities at the grass root level and to create more awareness about the health schemes for women in India.

- Government policies and national legislation should be strictly reinforcing about violence, sexual physical attack, health care, education, housing, and income generation activities, for tribal women in the country.
- Government should train health-care staff and improve the empowerment of tribal women in India.
- Government should provide health insurance scheme for the security of Tribal women in India. Priority should be given if the covid-19 cases are found in tribal areas if they are any kind of problems immediate response, addressing the specific needs of tribal women in the country.

Conclusion :- The study concludes that, the tribals are most disadvantaged sections of the Indian society they deprived of basic amenities like health, education and poor drinking water. As per the study reveals that tribal women are poor access to health, literacy, and nutritional status as compared to general population. To minimize the gap between tribal women and general population government should enact effectively implementation of health initiatives schemes, and laws, to minimize the disparities in health status and exploitation of tribal women in the future India.

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